

Ti^{IV} (5), Cr^{IV} (7), Cu^{II} (15) and Ca^{II} (30) and the rare earth metals (2) interferes (amounts in parenthesis, μg) seriously in the amperometric and photometric determinations of Se and Te with chromotropic acid.

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Spectrophotometric Study on Complexation Reaction of Copper(II) with *N*-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzylidene)hydrazine Carbothioamide

H. SANKE GOWDA*, S. MAQBOOL AHMED
and

K. S. JAGADEESH

Department of Chemistry, Central College, Bangalore University,
Bangalore-560 001

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A review of colorimetric reagents for copper(II) showed that no attempt was made to study the complexation reaction between copper and *N*-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazine carbothioamide (HMBHC). We report here our studies on the orange-yellow complex of copper with HMBHC. An analytical method has been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram amounts of copper. The advantages of the proposed method are high sensitivity, selectivity, simplicity and rapidity of determination without the need for extraction, heating or catalyst. Table 1 shows a comparison of HMBHC with some reagents¹⁻⁶ proposed for the determination of copper(II).

Experimental

A Beckman DB spectrophotometer with matched 1-cm silica cells was used for absorbance measure-

ments. pH of the solutions was measured (versus saturated calomel electrode) with a Elico L1-10 pH meter.

A stock solution of copper(II) was prepared from cupric sulphate pentahydrate (A.R.), standardised gravimetrically by the thiocyanate method⁷ and diluted to give a solution containing 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper(II). HMBHC was prepared by the condensation of hydrazine carbothioamide with vanillin and purified⁸. A 0.3% (w/v) solution of HMBHC was prepared in 90% aqueous ethanol (v/v). Solutions of hydrochloric acid-potassium chloride, hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate, acetic acid-sodium acetate and potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffers and diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared from analytical grade reagents.

Procedure: An aliquot of the stock solution (containing 5-77.5 μg of Cu^{II}), potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer solution (5 ml; pH 11.98), ethanol (6 ml) and 0.3% HMBHC solution (4 ml) were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark with double-distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 410 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of copper(II) was deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

HMBHC forms an orange-yellow complex with copper(II) instantaneously at room temperature ($28 \pm 1^\circ$) in acid, alkaline or buffer medium. Acid or alkaline medium was not preferred as the stability and sensitivity of the complex were very much less. The study of the complex in the buffers indicated that potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide is the most suitable buffer and the maximum absorbance is obtained over the pH range 9.3-11.6. The investigation of the effect of ethanolic concentration on the formation of complex showed that the maximum colour development is observed in the ethanolic concentration range 24-64% (v/v). Below this range the solution gave turbidity and above it maximum absorbance was not obtained. Hence a pH value of 11.2 and 40% (v/v) ethanolic medium in which the absorbance readings are stable for 75 min were selected.

The orange-yellow complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 408-412 nm where copper(II) and the reagent did not absorb appreciably (Fig. 1). The effect of reagent concentration was examined by measuring the absorbance at 410 nm of solutions containing 1.5 ppm of copper(II) and varying amounts of the reagent. A 45-fold molar excess of the reagent over copper(II) was required to obtain maximum absorbance. The effect of varying temperature on the stability of the complex was investigated. The absorbance value was not affected over the temperature range 6-48°. Above 48° the absorbance gradually decreased with increasing temperature. No appreciable change in

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF HMBHO WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC REAGENTS FOR Cu^{II}

Sl. no.	Reagent	ϵ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	λ_{max} (nm)	Range of determination (ppm)	Most interfering ions
1.	Potassium cyanide	1.13×10^5	285	1–10	Au ^{III} , Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Fe ^{II}
2.	Ammonium 1-pyrrolidine carbothioate	1.8×10^5	269	0.2–4.0	—
3.	1-Isonitroso-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenazine	9.2×10^5	350	0–12	—
4.	2,8-Quinoxaline dithiol	2.25×10^5	625	0.1–1.0	Fe ^{II}
5.	p-Anisaldehyde thiosemicarbazone	6.1×10^5	402	0.2–9.8	Co ^{II} , Cr ^{VI}
6.	Hydrazinecarbothioamide-2-[diphenylmethylene]	1.82×10^4	360	0.5–3.5	Cr ^{VI} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , Ag ^I
7.	Hydrazinecarbothioamide-2-[9-furanylmethylene]	3.35×10^4	364	0.1–1.0	Co ^V , Ni ^{II} , Ag ^I
8.	HMBHO	1.23×10^4	410	0.2–8.1	Ti ^{IV}

Fig. 1

the absorbance was observed when the order of addition of the reactants was varied.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.1–3.2 ppm of copper(II). The optimum concentration range for the effective spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) by Ringbom's method was found to be 0.2–3.1 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity was found to be 5.15 ng cm⁻² and the molar absorptivity 1.23×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 410 nm. The standard deviation calculated from six determinations in a solution containing 1.5 ppm of copper(II) was 0.003 and the relative error was less than 2%.

The stoichiometric ratio of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variations, mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods and was found to be 1:2 (metal:ligand); the apparent stability constant of the complex evaluated by molar-ratio method was $\log k = 11.2 \pm 0.1$ at 28°. The electrolytic nature of the complex was found by ion-exchange experiments. When a very dilute solution of the complex was passed through a Dowex 50W-X8 cation-exchange column the orange-yellow colour was completely adsorbed. The eluate was colourless. When a Dowex 1-X8 anion-exchange column was used the eluate was orange-yellow. This indicates that the copper-HMBHC complex is cationic.

Interference study: The effects of some foreign ions which often accompany copper have been studied by adding the ions in different amounts to 1.5 ppm of copper in solution. The following amounts (ppm) of foreign ions were found to give less than 2% error in the determination of 1.5 ppm of copper(II): Zn^{II}, 20; Ba^{II}, 10; Ca^{II}, 10; Fe^{III}, 6; Co^{II}, 0.5; Ni^{II}, 0.5; Al^{III}, 14; As^{III}, 104; Pb^{II}, 24; Ag^I, 3; Mn^{II}, 100; Mg^{II}, 24; W^{VI}, 80; Au^{III}, 5; U^{VI}, 30; Te^{VI}, 31; Sb^{III}, 16; Zr^{IV}, 15; Bi^{III}, 6; Ti^{IV}, 1.5; Sn^{II}, 27; Sn^{IV}, 32; Cr^{III}, 146; Hg^{II}, 36; V^V, 40; sulphate, 8000; nitrate and thiosulphate 10000; phosphate, 3500; oxalate, 80; citrate and tartrate, 7000; fluoride, 8500; chloride and bromide, 9000; iodide, 860; EDTA, 160. The tolerance limit of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II} and Ag^I could be raised to 24, 4, 2.5, 140 and 5 ppm respectively by adding 100 ppm of EDTA, and that of Zn^{II}, Al^{III}, Sn^{II} and Sn^{IV} be raised to 28, 36, 520 and 47 ppm respectively by adding 3000 ppm of phosphate.

Application: The proposed method was used for the determination of copper in synthetic mixtures corresponding to the composition of copper alloys. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Cu IN COPPER ALLOYS

Sl. no.	Sample	Composition	Copper ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	
			Taken	Found*
1.	Steel backed copper-lead automotive bearing	Cu 2, Sn 8, Pb 90	0.50	0.49
			1.50	1.50
			2.50	2.48
2.	High tin babbitts	Cu 8.5, Sn 87.5, Sb 4	1.00	1.00
			2.00	2.01
			3.00	2.98
3.	Duralumin	Cu 4, Mg 0.5, Mn 0.5, Al 95	0.80	0.81
			1.60	1.61
			2.40	2.88
4.	Y-alloy	Cu 4, Ni 2, Mg 1, Al 93	0.90	0.90
			1.80	1.81
			2.80	2.78
5.	E-alloy	Cu 2.5, Zn 20, Mg 0.5, Mn 0.5, Al 76.5	0.60	0.60
			1.60	1.59
			2.60	2.61
6.	Silver coin	Cu 40, Ag 50, Ni 5, Zn 5	0.80	0.79
			1.80	1.80
			2.80	2.82

* Average of five determinations.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) and Copper(II) with 2,6-Pyridinediol

SHASHI K. BANSAL, SHIELLA TIKKU,
SUMAN SHREY and R. S. SINDHU*

Chemistry Department, Regional College of Education,
Ajmer-305 004

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SOME of the hydroxypyridines are used widely as analytical reagents in the determination of different metal ions¹⁻⁵. The present communication reports the use of 2,6-pyridinediol as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Experimental

Double-distilled water and A. R. grade chemicals were used. Stock solutions of ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate and 2,6-pyridinediol (Aldrich) were prepared in double-distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the chloride or nitrate salts of cations, and from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of anions.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using an Universal 14 spectrophotometer. pH measurements were made using an Elico pH meter.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 1–84 µg of Fe^{II} or 1.2–116 µg of Cu^{II}, were added 20 times of 2,6-pyridinediol solution in case of Fe^{II} system and 15 times in case of Cu^{II} system, and pH values of the solutions was adjusted to 7–10.2 and 7.5–10.8 respectively. In case of Fe^{II}, the solution was heated for 0.5 h while for Cu^{II} no heating was required. For both the ions, the volume was made upto 20 ml by adding double-distilled water, and absorbance was measured at 420 and 535 nm in case of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively, against the reagent blank, and the amount evaluated by a calibration curve.

Results and Discussions

When aqueous solutions of Cu^{II} and 2,6-pyridinediol were mixed at different concentrations and at different pH values formation of the coloured

complex took place immediately. In case of Fe^{II}, while following same procedure, no coloured complex was formed in cold but when the solution was heated on a water-bath for 30 min, formation of the coloured complex took place. The absorption spectra of different systems were recorded and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF Fe^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES WITH 2,6-PYRIDINEDIOL

Characteristic	Fe ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	420	535
Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^3$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	10.8	14.2
Reagent needed	20 times	15 times
pH range	7–10.2	7.5–10.8
Beer's law range (ppm)	upto 4.8	upto 6.6
Range of determination (ppm)	0.5–4.2	0.6–5.8
Metal–ligand ratio (Jobs method)	1 : 2	1 : 2
Standard deviation (Metal ion concn., ppm)	0.0078 (3.5)	0.0042 (3.0)

Effect of diverse ions: The study was carried out in solutions containing 3.5 ppm of Fe^{II} or Cu^{II} and in presence of the desired amounts of foreign ions. After following the recommended procedure the absorbance was noted. The tolerance limits (in parenthesis, ppm) of different anions and cations in determinations of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} are as follows: for both Fe and Cu, fluoride (100), chloride (1000), bromide (1500), EDTA (5), Zn^{II} (50), Cd^{II} (100), Hg^{II} (500), Mn^{II} (200), Co^{II} (100) and Ni^{II} (100); for Fe only, nitrate (500), thiosulphate (20) and Cu^{II} (1.5); for Cu only, nitrate (1000), thiosulphate (10) and Fe^{II} (100).

Applications: The method was applied in the determination of iron and copper in their alloys. The solutions of the alloys were prepared as described in literature⁶. In each case, six determinations were made. Analysis of N. K. K. 920 alloy gave iron content 0.718% (0.72% certified value) with a standard deviation of 0.01. In brass, Cu content was found to be 64.983% (65.0% certified value) with a standard deviation 0.007.

Comparison with other reagents: A comparison with other spectrophotometric reagents shows that 2,6-pyridinediol ranks among the highly sensitive reagents (Table 2).

TABLE 2—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC REAGENTS FOR Fe^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH 2,6-PYRIDINEDIOL

Metal ion	Reagent	Molar absorptivity dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Fe ^{II}	Methyl-2-pyridyl ketoxime ^a	14.0 × 10 ³
	Biacetylmonoxime thiosemicarbazone ^b	11.5 × 10 ³
	4-Amino-2-mercapto-5-nitroso-6-pyrimidinediol ^c	6.1 × 10 ³
	5-Chloro-2,3-pyridinediol ^d	2.5 × 10 ³
Cu ^{II}	Biacetylmonoxime semicarbazone ^e	10.1 × 10 ³
	Benzimidazole-2-carboxanilide oxime ^f	14.5 × 10 ³
	4-Imino-1,3-dimethylalloxan-5-oxime ^g	5.1 × 10 ³
	Rutin ^h	8.1 × 10 ³
	Ortho aminophenol ⁱ	10.6 × 10 ³

^aRef. 7, ^bRef. 8, ^cRef. 9, ^dRef. 10, ^eRef. 11, ^fRef. 12, ^gRef. 13, ^hRef. 14, ⁱRef. 15.